

A Comparative Study of Chemisorption of Oxygen and the Accompanying Changes in Electrical Conductivity on Irradiated and Non-Irradiated Vanadium Pentoxide Catalysts

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A comparative study has been made on chemisorption of oxygen and the accompanying changes in electrical conductivity on Vanadium pentoxide catalyst irradiated with 14.8 Mev neutrons and on non-irradiated catalyst sample within the temperature range, 50-200°C. Increased rate and amount of chemisorption of oxygen and greater percentage decrease in conductivity have been observed in the irradiated sample than in the non-irradiated one. This has been explained as being due to a greater defect concentration in the former case. Most of the radiation-induced defects, however, get slowly annealed at higher temperatures.

THE primary effects of interaction of matter with high energy radiations are electronic excitations, ionisation, displacement of atoms and transmutations¹. Radiation can, therefore, be used as a suitable source for introducing defects into solids and hence for increasing the efficiency of the selectivity of catalysts. In fact, a number of workers²⁻⁷ have observed the change in the energy of activation of specific chemical reactions after the interaction of the catalyst with high energy radiations. Literature survey does not reveal any information on the effect of radiation on the adsorption capacity of V_2O_5 catalyst.

In this paper, the results of comparative study of chemisorption of oxygen and the accompanying changes in electrical conductivity on vanadium pentoxide catalyst irradiated with 14.8 Mev neutrons and also on non-irradiated catalyst sample have been presented. This study also includes determination of surface area, pore structure, pore size distribution, ESR study, etc.

Experimental

Preparation of the Catalysts

Non-irradiated V_2O_5 :—Pure vanadyl oxalate was obtained by adding stoichiometric quantity of A.R. ammonium metavanadate to a hot solution of A.R. oxalic acid with constant stirring. The contents were slowly evaporated on a water-bath with

intermittent stirring to almost dryness. The solid mass thus obtained was heated at a temperature of 110°C in an air-oven for 12 hours. The lumps were then cut into pieces and were decomposed in a pyrex reactor at a temperature of 420-440°C for four hours with a constant flow of air. These lumps were pulverised and particles between - 100 to + 120 mesh size (B.S.) were selected for the adsorption and surface area measurements.

Irradiated V_2O_5 :—The powdered non-irradiated V_2O_5 was degassed at 200°C for 6 hours at 10^{-5} torr and then sealed in a soft glass tube of about 0.5 mm. thickness and irradiated by the neutron generator. The sample was bombarded at room temperature with neutron flux of 5.0×10^{12} nvt with an integrated dose of 10^{17} n/cm². The neutron source was tritium, adsorbed on platinum metals and bombarded by 200 Kev deuterons. The energy liberated (17.58 Mev) was distributed over α -particles and neutrons. α -particles were cut off by a copper foil and neutrons of 14.8 Mev were used for the bombardment.

After irradiation the substance was transferred to the catalyst tube and degassed for 3-5 hours at 200°C and then adsorption was studied as usual. Exactly the same evacuation technique was followed with the non-irradiated sample. In case of the irradiated catalyst it was changed after each experiment as the radiation-induced effects might gradually anneal due to successive heat treatments.

Adsorption and Electrical Conductivity Measurements

All adsorption measurements were carried out in a conventional volumetric adsorption apparatus described previously by Bhattacharyya, Ramchandran and Ghosh⁸. The surface area of the sample was measured by adsorbing pure dry nitrogen at -195°C and the cross-section of nitrogen molecule was taken to be 16.2 \AA^2 . In all adsorption measurements the dead space was calibrated by pure dry helium gas at different temperatures.

The resistance of the pelleted sample was measured by an electronic dc voltmeter, details of the methods and procedure being already given by Calderbank⁹. The specimen used for conductivity measurements was prepared by compressing vanadium pentoxide powders under a pressure of about 45 kg/cm^2 into a pellet of about $9 \text{ mm dia.} \times 5 \text{ mm thickness}$. Fresh pellets were used for each electrical conductivity experiment.

here. Hence these changes are most probably due to sintering or smoothening of the surface radiation.

Electrical Conductivity Studies

In case of conductivity measurements the results are represented as the percentage change in conductivity ($\Delta C/C\%$), where C is the conductance in vacuum and ΔC is the change in conductivity due to the adsorption of the gas.

Preliminary experiments showed that the temperature at which the irradiated catalysts were degassed before starting actual conductivity experiments had great influence on the values of ($\Delta C/C$)% as a function of temperature. Therefore, the effect of degassing temperature was studied to determine the approximate limit below which the annealing of the radiation-induced defects does not occur appreciably. This range was found to be within 150° – 200°C . The results are recorded in Table 2. Keeping the

TABLE 1. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VANADIUM PENTOXIDE

Sample	Total Pore-volume (ml)	Porosity	Average Pore radius	Pore with radius smaller than 182 \AA	BET surface area, m^2/gm
Non-irradiated	0.8952	0.830	1755 \AA	2.79%	10.2
Irradiated	0.7950	0.793	1370 \AA	4.02%	11.6

Results and Discussions*Physical Characteristics of the Catalysts*

The physical characteristics of the catalysts are presented in Table 1. The surface area has been found to be independent of the degassing temperature within the range of 150° to 300°C . The pore volume and the average pore radius of the catalysts were determined by a mercury porosimeter (Aminco, Model 5-7107). The results in Table 1 indicate that the pore volume goes down by 11%, the average pore radius goes down by 22%, whereas, the surface area goes up by 14% in case of irradiated catalyst.

These small changes in physical characteristics after irradiation cannot be taken as an index of structural modification by radiation. Such structural modifications are pronounced if the energy of radiation exceeds $10^{23} \text{ eV/gm}^{10}$ which is evidently not the case

degassing temperature at 165° , well within this range, the conductivity measurements were carried out at 50° , 75° , 100° , 125° , 150° , 175° , and 200°C for both irradiated and non-irradiated catalysts. The experimental data ($\Delta C/C$)% at different temperatures and different oxygen pressures are not tabulated or shown graphically but the main observations are summarised below. Only the results at oxygen pressure of 16 cm. at different temperatures are presented in Table 3 and shown graphically in fig. 1.

Clark and Berets¹¹, Butler¹², Bhattacharyya and Mahanti^{13,14} have shown that vanadium pentoxide is an n-type semiconductor due to the presence of quasi-free electrons in its lattice and that anionic chemisorption of oxygen takes place resulting in a depletion of current carriers and have a decrease in electrical conductivity.

For both the samples the values of ($\Delta C/C$)% (negative) increased with increasing experimental

TABLE 2. EFFECT OF DEGASSING TEMPERATURE ON THE CONDUCTIVITY OF V_2O_5 CATALYST PELLETS,
 $\frac{\Delta C}{C}$ %—PERCENTAGE CHANGE IN CONDUCTIVITY DUE TO OXYGEN ADSORPTION.

Expt. Temp. 100°C			Expt. Temp. 150°C			Expt. Temp. 200°C		
Temp. of degassing	Equilibrium $\frac{\Delta C}{C}$ %		Temp. of degassing	Equilibrium $\frac{\Delta C}{C}$ %		Temp. of degassing	Equilibrium $\frac{\Delta C}{C}$ %	
	Irradiated	Non-irradiated		Irradiated	Non-irradiated		Irradiated	Non-irradiated
100°C	40.60	18.00	150°C	71.5	32.10	200°C	63.90	44.20
150°C	41.60	20.10	200°C	64.00	34.00	250°C	61.60	50.10
200°C	41.30	22.00	250°C	58.90	35.20	300°C	55.80	50.70
250°C	37.10	21.60	300°C	40.40	34.10	350°C	44.90	43.60
300°C	25.02	18.20	350°C	35.10	34.20	400°C	41.30	41.80
350°C	17.80	17.10	400°C	33.00	34.00			
400°C	18.10	16.50						

temperature. This indicates increased chemisorption with temperature. At any temperature below 150°C the values of $(\Delta C/C)\%$ for the irradiated sample were always higher than those of non-irradiated sample. This increase was found to be almost two fold in certain temperature. The values of $(\Delta C/C)\%$ for the irradiated sample, at any experimental temperatures below 150°C, was found to be much higher even at the lowest ambient oxygen pressure when compared with the non-irradiated sample at the highest oxygen pressure. This increase in the $(\Delta C/C)\%$ for the irradiated sample continued upto 150°C and then slowly decreased till 175°C and thereafter increased again with temperature. The decrease in $(\Delta C/C)\%$ in the temperature range, 150–175°C, might presumably be due to fast annealing of radiation defects, if any, created due to radiation. Increase in temperature probably had a greater effect on the annealing of the defects than chemisorption of oxygen on the surface, the net effect being less chemisorption and decrease in the value of $(\Delta C/C)\%$. In the temperature range, 175° to 200°C, probably the effect of temperature was greater on chemisorption than on the annealing of the remainder defects. This behaviour is evident from the isobar plot (Fig. 1).

Hence from the above discussion we can explain the enhanced chemisorption as well as the annealing effect with temperature if we assume that certain changes, not physical in nature, took place during irradiation.

Fig. 1. Conductivity Isobar for Oxygen Chemisorption at a constant pressure of 16.0 cm.

The primary effects of high energy radiation on materials are (a) electronic excitation, (b) ionisation, (c) formation of pointdefects and (d) transmutation. Of the four main types of changes expected, the ionisation probability, in this case, is much less as neutron has very low ionising capacity. The artificial transmutation chances are very little as the neutrons are very fast (5×10^{12} nvt) and the neutron capture cross section of vanadium corresponding to 14.75 Mev of neutron (monoenergetic source) is only 2.5 barns/cm².

The sample was tested for radioactivity by M.G. Counter immediately after the bombardment but

did not show any sign of radioactivity. The capture cross section 2.5 barns/cm² is perhaps too small for (n, p), (n, 2n), (n, α) types of reactions. The capture cross sections for (n-n) and (n-n γ) types of reactions are very small. So some types of reaction leading to the formation of point defects might be more probable effects of radiation in this case.

The increase in electrical resistance of V₂O₅ (n-type semi-conductor) above the room temperature due to oxygen adsorption both in case of irradiated and non-irradiated samples is in good agreement with the anionic chemisorption on n-type semiconductor.

As expected, irradiation might have produced some displacement of atoms. If oxygen atoms are displaced from the lattice position then owing to their large atomic volume they cannot be accommodated in the interstitial positions but fall into existing vacancies. Thus they may accumulate inside the lattice or may leave the solid passing into the gaseous phase. On the other hand, if vanadium atoms are displaced then they may remain in the interstitial position in their valence states and leave vacancies in the lattice. These interstitial atoms will behave as donor centres. This picture would be different from that of oxygen vacancies which are assumed to be responsible for the electronic properties of V₂O₅.

TABLE 3. CHANGE IN THE CONDUCTIVITY OF V₂O₅ CATALYST PELLET DUE TO OXYGEN ADSORPTION

Temp. °C	-($\Delta C/C$)%	
	Irradiated	Non-irradiated
55	24.05	10.10
75	30.10	17.50
100	40.05	22.45
125	44.00	32.05
150	67.50	34.95
175	47.00	35.05
200	64.50	40.00

ESR Studies

Ioffe and Patrino¹⁵ have observed a very weak or no signal in ESR for V₂O₅ sample and this increased by gradual addition of promoters because of formation of solid solution. Tarama and coworkers¹⁶ have obtained a single broad ESR spectrum for V₂O₅.

The measurements, in our case, were carried out with an ESR spectrometer (Bruber-Physik A.G., Model No. B-ER 402) at both room temperature and liquid air temperature. The experiments were done in presence of air taking 0.3350 gms. of powdered catalyst in a quartz sample tube (2 mm dia \times 12 cm. length). Both the spectra are essentially of the same nature in case of both irradiated and non-irradiated samples. This probably means that no new type of magnetic defects are introduced into the lattice during irradiation. When same quantities of both the samples are taken the amplitude of the signal corresponding to the irradiated sample is found to be larger than the non-irradiated sample. This may be due to an increase in the spin concentration in the former case. Though the 'g' value is between the values for DPPH and the free electrons (2.0036 and 2.0023, respectively) it does not mean that they are behaving more as free electrons than as bound electron. After all the electron on the DPPH is bound. What it does mean is that the orbital contribution is largely quenched.

Kinetics of Chemisorption of Oxygen

The kinetics of chemisorption of oxygen has been measured at 55°, 150°, and 200°C for both irradiated and non-irradiated V₂O₅ with 10.0 gms of catalyst under a constant pressure of 41.80 cms. The rate of adsorption is very slow and is preceded by a massive fast adsorption with different kinetics and the adsorption equilibrium is not attained even after 720 mins. It has been observed that the kinetic data obey the Elovich equation¹⁷, the integrated form of which is :

$$q = \frac{2.3}{\alpha} \log(t + t_0) - \frac{2.3}{\alpha} \log t_0 + q_0$$

where, α = deceleration constant of the process,
 t_0 = an arbitrary constant chosen for linearisation of q vs. $\log(t + t_0)$ plots and $t_0 = (1/\alpha a)$,
 a = initial rate of uptake at $t=0$,
 q_0 = volume of gas adsorbed at $t=0$.

Figs. 2 and 3 represent the Elovich plots of q vs. $\log(t + t_0)$ for the non-irradiated and irradiated catalysts

Fig. 2. Elovich plots for non-irradiated Vanadium Pentoxide.

Fig. 3. Elovich plots for irradiated Vanadium Pentoxide.

respectively. Particularly in case of irradiated catalyst a few initial points do not fall in the straight line and this is most probably due to the continuation of the initial massive adsorption of different kinetics¹⁸. The results of kinetic measurements have been summarised in Table 4.

From Table 4 it is evident that the initial rate of uptake 'a' increases with temperature from 55° to 200°C in case of the non-irradiated sample. The same trend is observed for the irradiated sample upto 150°C but beyond this temperature the initial rate of uptake decreases with temperature. However, the initial rate of uptake is always greater for the irradiated sample than for the non-irradiated sample within the temperature range of 150°C.

In case of α -values the behaviour of the irradiated sample is distinctly different from that of the non-irradiated one. In the former case, the α -values are lower denoting the greater rate of chemisorption. Moreover, α -values for the irradiated sample increase with temperature thus denoting a negative temperature coefficient of the reaction rate, whereas in case of non-irradiated sample, the reverse is observed. These observations are more pronounced in the temperature range, 150°–200°C, where the radiation induced defects are annealed fast. This accounts for the observed anomalous slope of the Elovich plot at 200°C for irradiated V_2O_5 (Fig. 3). Table 4 also indicates that at this temperature the α -values for irradiated V_2O_5 is nearly identical with that for non-irradiated V_2O_5 .

The initial massive adsorption, q_0 , is not independent of temperature, as observed by Taylor and Thon¹⁹, but increases with increasing temperature indicating that the fast adsorption process is also an activated one. Almost similar results were obtained by Charman and Dell²⁰, where the initial fast adsorption on NiO greatly increased with irradiated oxide, continued for 100 secs., and then followed the Elovich kinetics. The greater initial massive adsorption on irradiated sample will result in the overall increased adsorption on irradiated sample

TABLE 4. ANALYSIS OF ELOVICH PLOTS FOR KINETICS OF OXYGEN CHEMISORPTION ON VANADIUM PENTOXIDE $\left(\frac{dq}{dt} = a.e^{-\alpha q}\right)$

Temperature °C	Non-irradiated V_2O_5				Irradiated V_2O_5			
	t_0 (min.)	a (c.c. ⁻¹ gm)	$a \times 10^3$ (c.c.min ⁻¹ gm ⁻¹)	q_0 (c.c.gm ⁻¹)	t_0 (min.)	a (c.c. ⁻¹ gm)	$a \times 10^3$ (c.c.min ⁻¹ gm ⁻¹)	q_0 (c.c.gm ⁻¹)
55	3	223.0	1.49	0.25	5	51.9	3.85	0.42
100	3	110.0	3.03	0.29	3	50.2	6.64	0.61
150	2	105.5	4.73	0.42	2	64.4	7.76	0.83
200	0.5	96.2	20.70	0.60	3.5	76.9	3.71	0.62

than on non-irradiated one. This is also corroborated from the conductivity results.

Mechanism of Chemisorption of Oxygen

Melnick²¹ has pointed out that the logarithmic rate of chemisorption arises if the height of the activation barrier increases linearly with coverage. Therefore, in the case of diffusion of electrons from the bulk to the surface being the slowest step, the occurrence of Elovich equation can be explained. Hence the mechanism of oxygen chemisorption on vanadium pentoxide can be envisaged as the interaction of adsorbed oxygen atom with a free electron and a vacant surface anion site of the lattice :

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